

EXPLORERS

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Case Western Reserve University

Department of Electrical Engineering
and Computer Science

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Case Western Reserve University is the Top 1 research university in Ohio, with 17 Nobel laureates affiliated, ranked 32nd most innovative among national universities and 13th for commercialization of research.

The **Department of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science** at Case Western Reserve University is motivated by synergetic research thrust exploring the intersections of bio-micro-info in the ever-changing world of technology. We bring together a spectrum of degree programs and research thrusts that ultimately lead to the enhancement of life. We strive for distinction through excellence, productivity, and innovation. We emphasize a student-centric, experiential learning environment that prepares capable professionals, effective teammates, and life-long learners.

READY FOR:

OPEN IDEAS

x1 CHALLENGE

RESEARCHERS

INNOVATORS

FUNDED
BY

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 825183.

OPEN IDEAS

PROPOSE YOUR OWN IDEA

Submit openly a disruptive idea based on your line of research, product or service. Attract the interest of this US Node.

FOCUS TECHNOLOGY AREAS

AI	Blockchain
Big Data	IoT
5G	Cybersecurity
Cloud/Edge	

KEY APPLICATION SECTORS

Security
Health
Energy
Transport

CHALLENGE #9 - CWRU-SEC-01

→ Secure deep learning

Meet the expectations of this US Node through the technology challenge described below

DESCRIPTION

Security in deep learning

OBJECTIVES

Investigate security and privacy issues in deep learning; develop defense strategies; implement and validate the ideas.

SKILLS REQUIRED

Background on deep learning, cybersecurity, and privacy would be preferred

